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School-Based Management Committees For The Quality Administration Of Public Secondary Schools In Imo State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the school-based management committees for the quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were raised to guide the study. The descriptive survey design method was adopted. The population of this study consisted of 109,256 teachers and students in 296 public secondary schools in Imo State. The sample for this study was 400 teachers and students and a Proportionate stratified sampling technique to determine the appropriate minimum sample size was used to select the respondents. The instrument that was used for the collection of data in this study was a questionnaire. The questionnaire was titled Performance of School-Based Management Committee for Quality Administration of Public Secondary School Questionnaire. Three experts determined the face and content validities of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was established using the Cronbach alpha reliability test. The overall reliability stood at 0.95 which was considered reliable and adequate for the study. 400 copies of the instruments were administered, and 390 were retrieved the research questions for this study were answered using mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance using a z-test. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the appropriate performance of school-based management committees will improve and guarantee quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State, and it was recommended that The Government at both the Federal and State levels should formulate operational policy guidelines and enact appropriate laws to give legal backing and create an enabling environment for the effective operation of the SBMCs. This will no doubt ensure sustainable improvement in the quality of management and outputs of the Nigerian secondary education system.

Keywords: school-based management committees, quality administration, secondary schools, and Imo State.

INTRODUCTION

The school is a social organization that has an outstanding structure and system that controls the relationship and actions of its human resources for the growth and development of society. That is where formal education has undoubtedly remained the basic pillar of national growth and development likewise the vital tool for economic growth and technological innovation in any society. It is as a result of these perceptions that the government of Nigeria considers it right to invest numerous resources to ensure that the provision of education is geared towards reforms and policies that are valuable to the masses. This is because the standard educational system is the bedrock of any nation that strives to develop. In light of this, the government of Nigeria has over the years set and improved standards for the system of education

to be organized. Moreover, the education system needs to be established adequately with the collective efforts of the educational planners. The attempt to balance educational goals and societal needs results in what we know today as School-Based Management. School-based management can be regarded as the process by which responsibility for decision-making, coordination, and planning are situated within the schools and involve stakeholders on educational issues. Al-Ghefili and Hoque (2013) opine that School-Based Management (SBM) is the act of decentralizing educational issues by improving stakeholders' participation in schools. Ayena and Ibukun, (2013), state that school-based management is the way by which authority and power are relegated to important education planners to perform the lawful assignments in the review of policies of education for lasting governance to attain stipulated standards and quality. Learning results in schools. That is to say, School Management is the act of decentralization and delegating authority and power to necessary stakeholders on the management and administration of education issues to attain set educational goals.

It is noteworthy to conclude that the disparity in the learner's output is nothing to write home about. The Nigerian government deems it fit to ensure that the public system of education after the primary level is invested in but the results are not encouraging, due to the bureaucratic nature of the education system. The stakeholders that are supposed to be the sole planners and decision makers of these policies were sidelined therefore implementation of policies of education have become difficult since they are the facilitators as well as the beneficiaries. The useful and corresponding school-society partnership is a joint effort for a lasting-quality education (Ayeni, 2010).

Suffice it to say that the administrators of schools most times are appointed by the government in power without enough scrutiny to ensure the right thing is done, therefore school administrators sometimes find it difficult to implement vital policies due to the non-involvement of educational stakeholders. Quality and involvement of educational stakeholders. Quality administration of schools is a goal-oriented activity (Rawung, 2015). It encompasses group efforts, coordinated work, and performance geared towards set goal attainment in educational institutions. UNESCO (2010) stipulates that one of the numerous basic qualities of a country's level of development is education. Globally, education is regarded as a human right. This creates an enormous challenge for public secondary education policy in Imo State which needs to be re-organized to respond to inevitable demand and also exercise appropriate social and political will on issues concerning education at this level.

For this reason, there is a call for concern by the Imo State government and educational stakeholders to achieve quality education using generally accepted management strategies, and effective and worldwide scrutinized methods, which focus on collaboration and teamwork known as School-Based Management (SBM). National Council on Education in Ayeni and Ibukun (2013), asserts that the council encourages the creation of school-based management teams in all schools in Nigeria basically at the Primary and secondary levels which involves 12 to 19 stakeholders in each school. This aided and paved the way for a goal-oriented relationship between and among educational stakeholders in the Imo state. The government at the central level uses this, as one of the best reforms of education in the wider world especially in Nigeria, to ensure effective and quality administration of public secondary schools is upheld in Imo State to ensure effective and quality administration of public secondary schools is upheld in Imo State.

Statement of the Problem

School administration is becoming more complex and cumbersome as students, parents, and other stakeholders are becoming more aware of their rights especially as more funds are committed to schools by both government and private citizens. Stakeholders are demanding more than ever that they should have a voice in making decisions on what goes on in schools. Stakeholders participating in decision-making have argued that if decisions have to be implemented by education stakeholders, they will be highly inspired if they have a voice in making the decision. Several studies on group participation in decision-making in schools have revealed among others that participation in decision-making increases the morale of teachers, students, and other stakeholders. Moreover, the findings of some scholars state

that having a voice in decision-making increases understanding and generates group involvement and commitment. Regrettably, it seems that there is an absence of meaningful and effective participation in decision and policy-making processes by stakeholders of public secondary schools in Imo State to ensure the formulation of policies that are consistent with the needs of learners and their local community. This has deprived the citizens of quality secondary education and raised concerns among stakeholders. The involvement of education stakeholders in decision-making will make education policies more effective and their implementation easy. It is against this backdrop that the researcher is poised to assess the performance of School-Based Management Committees for the quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state, the level of role perceptions of school-based-management committee members for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state, the extent to which School-Based Management Committee members perform their roles in quality administration of public secondary school in Imo state, how school-based management committees generate fund and challenges of school-based management committee members for quality administration of public secondary school in Imo state form the elements of the problem.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to investigate the performance of school-based management committees for the quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Find out the functions of school-based management committees for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state.
2. Find out the challenges of school-based management committee members for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the functions of the school-based management committee for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state?
2. What are the challenges of school-based management committee members for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses formulated for this study were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of teachers and students on the functions of school-based management committees for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of teachers and students on the challenges of School-Based Management Committee members for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concepts of School-Based Management Committee

The Concept of school-based management committees stands as an important issue in the management of schools. School-based management committee as the name implies, is regarded as the stakeholders in education given decision-making authorities in schools so that educational issues are independently allocated, controlled, explored, and prioritized. SBMC is known as a significant tool for developing and encouraging community involvement in school decision-making (Kiragu in Prew 2018). Abu, in Kiragu, King Oina, and Migosi (2013) opine that the common theory for SBM is that education stakeholders should be allowed to participate in educational issues. Rawung (2015) asserts that SBMC consists of a group of people working together under the organizational design of a school to attain stipulated goals which can be seen through the improvement of educational quality and learning outcomes. A school-based management committee is a significant tool that ensures the collaboration of educational stakeholders in the decision-making process, improvement of accountability, supervision, evaluation of

stakeholders' performance, and management, and administration of schools to ensure qualitative learning outcomes (Ayeni and Ibukun 2013). In recent times, apart from the 2005 school-based management committee meetings, the earlier initiative and policies of education in Nigeria dates back to the year 2000 when the school-based management committees were adopted. The post-2000 education reforms in Nigeria also focus on Operation Reach All Secondary School (ORASS), community accountability, and transparent initiatives likewise read to be educated (Babahola & Atinmoni, 2009).

Educational stakeholders at the local level who pool resources to plan, monitor, strategize, and ensure the implementation process for achieving educational goals are known as SBMC (Prew, 2018). Activities related to school-based management must comply with national regulations, with educational activities organized within a framework of transparency, accountability, standards, and established policies by the necessary stakeholders in the school, referred to as SBMCS (Education Bureau, 2020). Asaya (2010) emphasizes the importance of SBMC as a crucial group of education stakeholders, highlighting the key principle of administration, which is the delegation of authority. In alignment with the above statement, Rawung (2015) defines the School Management Committee as stakeholders in school autonomy that oversee and address the needs of the school community, based on education laws and policies. This is consistent with the National Policy on Education, as stated in Anero (2014; p 40), which encourages collaboration, involvement, and participation of educational planners at different local levels in the administration and management of schools.

School-based management is the method by which decision-making in educational issues is decentralized thereby involving parents and the local communities (Al-ghafeili and Hoque, 2018). The purpose of school-based management relies on allowing schools to positively react quickly to parents' demands, make available educational opportunities for students, and aid in efficient and effective management of resources in schools (Mc Gowan, 2010). Supporting this view, Gurr-hill, Rolleston, Pherali, and Schendel (2015), explain that any group formed in which planning authority is devolved to the school level is referred to as a school-based management committee. SBMCs are the group that comprises members who are delegated with authority and power and willing to perform their assigned roles and responsibilities guided under law. The SBMC members abide by the policies for entry and exit of membership and provide support to encourage the schools and local communities to likewise ensure collaborative decision-making in schools geared towards the attainment of educational set goals (Federal Ministry of Education, 2011).

The Concept of Quality Administration

Quality, as the name implies, connotes high standards. According to Ayeni and Ibukun (2013; p. 30), quality encompasses all the activities carried out to meet set standards and expectations of society. Hornby (2015) also emphasizes that quality denotes a significant degree. Haron (2015) defines quality in education as a major avenue through which learners improve and achieve positive learning outcomes. Desired quality is achieved through adequate management focus on the attainment of set goals (McGowan, 2010). Quality can be seen as attaining the ultimate standards and valued performance that can lead to perfection. Quality in education is the standard set as the basic strategy that can encourage effective learning outcomes for students (Shmula, 2019).

Quality administration, on the other hand, is regarded as the procedure and result of involving all the educational aids and methods with a conducive climate to achieve set objectives by the organization in a given period (Rawung, 2015). Supporting the above assertion, Aljuboury (2010) states that the quality administration of schools is based on the satisfaction of stakeholders involved in education. This agrees with the view that quality administration in schools is the process by which the school manager controls the activities in the school geared towards the realization of set educational objectives. Ayeni and Ibukun (2013), opine that quality school administration depends to a great extent on the provision and efficient management of the human resources available. The school-based management committee has been delegated with the task of recruitment techniques, selection, training, compensation, and conditions of

employment. Hoque (2013), states that for quality administration to strive qualified human resources required for school administration and educational development should be provided.

Moreover, quality administration can be seen as the method used to perform activities that are in line with the laid down rules and regulations through avoidance of significant mistakes geared towards the realization of the expectations of the society and satisfaction of needs which invariably aid in the attainment of stipulated goals.

Functions of School-Based Management Committees for Quality Administration of Public Secondary Schools in Imo State

The School-Based Management Committee (SBMC) is a management framework led by a chairman elected from among the education stakeholders within the school. SBMC ensures curriculum and personnel development, proper utilization of school resources, and improved learning outcomes (Suhardan & Aryanti, 2019). SBMC members oversee the relevance of the curriculum, student enrollment, teacher commitment, and dissemination of educational information to deliver quality service using available educational facilities in schools (National Policy on Education, 2014). The government of Nigeria established SBMC to minimize the challenges in the administration and management of primary and secondary schools. SBMC was instituted by the Federal Ministry of Education in 2019 to ensure societal needs and educational goals are balanced for the growth and development of society Yusuf, Jagaba, and Jatau (2021). Every school is expected to have its team of education stakeholders. Meanwhile, the functions geared towards the realization of the main aim of the SBM team which is to ensure that the challenges facing the local school learners are identified, as well as their effects and ways the known barriers prevent the school administrators from carrying out their tasks (Federal Ministry of Education, 2011).

Rawung (2015) suggests that one of the functions of School-Based Management Committees (SBMC) is to ensure participatory decision-making by education stakeholders. According to Kenton (2019), SBMC is responsible for training people for jobs, as well as recruiting, selecting, and allocating beneficial programs to employees. SBMC, in terms of human resources management, helps managers plan, direct, and organize the administrative functions of the school. Ayeni and Ibukun (2013) define education stakeholders as individuals who contribute to an organization using their skills and knowledge. Nambuya (2013) emphasizes the role of SBMC in capacity building within the education system. The committee organizes human resources to address the needs and educational challenges of public secondary schools in Imo State through the implementation of a suitable curriculum. The Federal Ministry of Education (2011) emphasizes the importance of human resources for the overall growth and improvement of the school planning process. Furthermore, the SBMC prioritizes the ideas of professionals, training, and staff development in schools.

Challenges of School Base Management Committee Members for Quality Administration in Public Secondary Schools in Imo State

The activities of SBMCs based on their roles and responsibilities are posed with a lot of problems. Some of the challenges according to Ayeni and Ibukun (2013) are as follows: -

1. Unskilled stakeholders
2. Irregular specialized on-the-job training of the stakeholders:

Unskilled stakeholders

Some School-Based Management Committee (SBMC) members lack the necessary qualifications and skills to effectively handle educational issues in schools (Kiragu *et al.*, 2013). This is in line with the assertion that the employment of untrained and unqualified staff is a challenge in schools (Akinwumuji and Agabi, 2008). Some stakeholders lack knowledge of their roles and responsibilities, making it difficult for them to effectively perform their assigned roles, which can impact the quality of school administration. It is worth noting that some students in public secondary schools in Imo State are not learning due to unqualified and unskilled teachers. Adeyemo in Asikha (2010) states that unskilled and

unmotivated teachers' services can affect the performance of students. Similarly, Oswald in Ige (2020) states that if the stakeholders appointed in schools are qualified and skilled, quality administration geared towards educational goal attainment can be achieved.

Subjects are sometimes taught by individuals who are not qualified to teach them, which impacts the students negatively. This is why Kiragu *et al.* (2013) affirm that a lack of skilled stakeholders in schools can hinder quality administration. Supporting this assertion, Ololube (2013) states that unqualified and unskilled education stakeholders pose a serious challenge to quality administration to strive. The unavailability of adequate manpower in educational planning has posed a serious challenge for quality administration in public secondary schools in Imo State, as unqualified and unskilled stakeholders in education are involved in the educational planning process, leading to faulty planning decisions. This is in line with Adiele *et al.* (2017), who states that the common norm in planning education in our society is to engage those who are not experts in education planning. According to Ayeni and Ibukun (2013), inexperienced and less knowledgeable members hinder the progress of SBM reform.

Irregular specialized on-the-job training of the stakeholders:

Stakeholders in an organization need to engage in regular training and skill acquisition to be future-oriented and goal-seeking. Teachers often lack the necessary competencies to perform their roles due to a lack of training and skills. The success and quality of organizational administration in meeting societal demand, competition, and opportunities depend on the stakeholders' ability to cope with the various phases and challenges of the business environment. According to Duad (2015), stakeholders play a significant role in influencing the work outcome of an organization, and consistent training of workers is crucial for the attainment of required skills for better role performance, especially in schools. The purpose of regular specialized on-the-job training is to address performance deficiencies and improve the role performance of stakeholders. However, in public secondary schools in Imo State, there is a lack of capability-building programs and initiatives to aid career development through workshops seminars *et cetera* geared towards the acquisition of professional skills are not forthcoming; which poses a serious challenge in public secondary schools in Imo State. The absence of capacity building can cause the administrators and teachers to be backward in the trend of time.

Okeme (2014) states two (2) main obstacles to School-based Management Committees which are as follows:-

Administrative Problems: The changes in society can disrupt an initial plan of educational issues ranging from economic, sociological, technological, and political likewise educational issues. According to Adiele, Obasi, and Ohia (2017), the use of unconfirmed data in the planning of education has disrupted the smooth planning of education issues. Most of the data used in educational administration are forged and cannot be proved by the stakeholders involved. Ololube (2013) identifies some challenges in the management and administration of schools which are the Lack of adequate data for proper planning and likewise untimely and unavailability of the national budget and allocation to education stakeholders. In line with the above view, Odumodu, (2013) affirms that the lack of adequate planning for education issues has created a lot of challenges in its implementation.

Resistance to change: The people's views are not taken into consideration which may result in the unaccomplishment of desired planned policies and attainment of education goals. Some people can resist the influence of the authority, therefore they form cliques (informal groups) to fight against the policies. This is in line with the assertion, that the difference in norms and values between the schools and the local community poses a problem in the successful administration of educational organization (Uwaoma, 2011).

According to Ayeni and Ibukun (2013) include the following as challenges faced by stakeholders:

Role conflict. According to Asaya (2010), the major challenge of a formal group is role conflict. The administrator in the cause of performing his role may divert and deviate from his responsibility to ensure adequate administration and authority geared toward the attainment of the organization's goal is upheld. The disparity between the school administration and parents has posed a lot of challenges whereby either

stakeholders want to lead or take responsibility more than the other stakeholders. Most staff, more especially principals, have abandoned their roles and faced the financial aspects of school-based management. Lack of confidence or trust among stakeholders can lead to conflict.

Administratively, managing personnel in the institution has been one of the greatest problems in education institutions. Thus, school-based management committees are not left out of these inhibiting factors. Notwithstanding the numerous models for quality administration, some factors can impede the management as identified by scholars organizations, and leaders around the world including inadequate planning. Olorube (2013) concerning decision-making further states that inappropriate planning on how human and material resources can be used has posed a lot of challenges in the administration of schools.

Theoretical Review

The study utilized Juran's theory, which was developed by Joseph Moses Juran (1904-2004) in 1951. Juran, an electrical engineer from Romania, emphasized the importance of human resources in quality management. His theory posits that organizational improvement is achieved through planned activities and control. This theory is often referred to as the "Quality trilogy," encompassing quality planning, improvement, and quality control. According to Aljuboury (2010) and Walden (1994), the theory aligns with the idea that employee participation in activities such as teamwork, decision-making, and focusing on quality is crucial for quality improvement. Additionally, the theory outlines ten planning measures essential for total quality management, as documented by Damen (2017).

1. Knowledge of activities that can lead to improvement and the needs for it should be established to ensure development.
2. Goals must be set and targeted.
3. The goals of the organization must be achieved.
4. Capacity building must be available.
5. Establish the task to be accomplished.
6. Supervise and evaluate the rate of improvement.
7. Encourage the efforts of the employees.
8. Record and report the extent of the organization's achievement.
9. Focus on the organization's development for further achievements to be made.
10. The stage should be repeated continuously for the goals of the organization to be adequately attained.

School-based committees are education stakeholders that are using the available resources levied with the task to plan, monitor, strategize, and ensure the implementation process for the attainment of education goals (Prew 2018 P.2). Juran theory encourages the efforts of the employees which focus on the organization development for quality administration to strive.

The theory applies to all social and educational institutions such as the school. It also provides, an explanation of the efforts of the stakeholders in an organization that is geared towards set goal attainment. This is why by 2006 SBMCs were instituted as strategies to ensure communities and schools work together to enhance academic excellence and quality administration (UBE in Bakwaia and Yusuf 2016, P.1). The capacity building of the stakeholders according to the theory should be made available. Sequel to Juran's theory of Total Quality Management, tasks must be established, that is, assigning roles to stakeholders, and goals must be set and targeted thereby resulting in the attainment of the set goals. The theory is also relevant to the study because it identifies the knowledge of the functions of educational stakeholders and the need for them, the roles of the stakeholders as tasks to be accomplished, how the individual roles are performed through records and reports to know the extent of organization achievement, irrespective of the challenges focus are on the organization development for further achievement to be recorded. These will be examined in the study as the variables of School-Based Management Committees for quality administration.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey design. The descriptive survey design describes the characteristics of the population studied and gathers data about research variables. The population of this study consisted of 109,256 teachers and students in 296 public secondary schools in Imo State. The sample for this study was 400 teachers and students and a Proportionate stratified sampling technique to determine the appropriate minimum sample size was used to select the respondents. The researcher used a researcher-made instrument (questionnaire) to gather information for the study. The instruments were tagged “Performance of School-Based Management Committee for Quality Administration of Public Secondary School Questionnaire” (PSBMCQAPSSQ). The research instrument was validated by two experts in the Department of Measurement and Evaluation who ascertained the content and constructed validities of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was established using the Cronbach alpha reliability test. The overall reliability stood at 0.95 which was considered reliable and adequate for the study. The researcher with the help of three research assistants administered 400 copies of the questionnaires to the respondents after a preliminary introduction and completed copies of the questionnaire and 390 which is 98% were retrieved. The responses from the research instrument were evaluated using the mean score and standard deviation for the research questions. The criterion mean of 2.5 was used to decide to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance using a z-test.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What are the functions of the school-based management committee for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state?*

Table 4.1: Mean scores and standard deviation of teachers and students on the functions of the school-based management committee for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state.

SN	Institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection availability Variable	Respondents				Mean Set X_1X_2	Decision
		Teachers = 163		Students =237			
		X_1	SD_1	X_2	SD_2		
1	participate in planning and decision-making processes in the school	3.42	0.49	3.45	0.49	3.34	Accepted
2	They ensure the relevance of the curriculum to the environment and the local community	1.85	0.52	2.01	0.60	1.93	Rejected
3	Ensure information on educational issues is adequately transmitted to the school	3.26	0.43	3.24	0.46	3.25	Accepted
4	support to provide funds through payment of fees.	3.32	0.69	3.25	0.72	3.28	Accepted
5	Set up mercenaries to check the enrolment of students	2.98	0.84	2.94	0.81	2.96	Accepted
6	Adequate educational facilities are used in school	2.96	0.87	2.86	0.89	2.91	Accepted
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		2.96	0.64	2.95	0.66	2.95	

Data in Table 4.1: presents the mean scores and standard deviation of teachers and students on the functions of a school-based management committee for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state. The average mean scores for the teachers and students are 2.96 and 2.95 respectively. Based on the average mean set score of 2.95 which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, it implies that both teachers and students accepted items 1, 3, 4, 5, and 6 as the functions of the school-

based management committee for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state. However, the teachers and students rejected item 2 as not part of the functions of the school-based management committee for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state.

Research Question Five: *What are the challenges of school-based management committee members for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State?*

Table 4.5: Mean scores and standard deviation of teachers and students on the challenges of school-based management committee members for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State

SN	Challenges Implementation variable	Respondents				Mean Set X ₁ X ₂	Decision
		Teachers = 163		Students =237			
		X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂		
25	Teachers notice indiscipline among students	1.75	0.87	1.66	0.82	1.70	Rejected
26	Inadequate funding of schools by the government	2.07	0.87	2.07	0.91	2.07	Rejected
27	Interference from the students' parents	2.74	0.87	2.78	0.86	2.76	Accepted
28	Lack of qualified and skilled teachers	3.28	0.74	3.16	0.76	3.22	Accepted
29	Unavailability of Teaching aids and materials	2.88	0.78	2.83	0.77	2.85	Accepted
30	Change in technology	3.29	0.68	3.31	1.40	3.30	Accepted
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		2.66	0.80	2.63	0.75	2.64	

Data in Table 4.5 presents the mean scores and standard deviation of teachers and students on the challenges of school-based management committee members for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State. The average mean scores are 2.66 for the teachers and 2.63 for the students. Based on the average mean set score of 2.64 which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, it implies that both teachers and students accepted 27, 28, 29, and 30 as the challenges of school-based management committee members for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State. However, the respondents rejected items 25 and 26 as not part of the challenges of school-based management committee members for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State. These include; Teachers noticing indiscipline among students and Inadequate funding of schools by the government.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teachers and student respondents on the functions of school-based management committees for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state.

Table 4.1: Z-test analysis on the Difference between the Mean Rating Scores of teachers and students on the functions of school-based management committees for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state.

Category	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	z-cal	z-crit.	Remarks
Teachers	163	2.96	0.64	388	0.158	±1.96	Not Significant
Students	237	2.95	0.66	2			Accept H ₀₁ (z-cal.< z-crit.)
Total	390			390			

Table 4.1 uncovered that teachers have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.96 and 0.64, while students have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.95 and 0.66 respectively. With a level of flexibility of 388 at an alpha noteworthy level of 0.05; the figured z-estimation of 0.158 is lesser than the z-critical of 1.96. Along these lines, the null hypothesis is accepted. By implication, there is no significant difference in the mean scores of teachers and student respondents on the functions of school-based management committees for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state.

H₀₅: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teachers and students on the Challenges of School-Based Management Committee members in quality administration in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Table 4.5: Z-test analysis on the Difference between the Mean Rating Scores of teachers and students on the Challenges of School-Based Management Committee members in quality administration in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Category	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit.	Remarks
Teachers	163	2.66	0.80	388	0.38	±1.96	Significant
Students	237	2.63	0.75	2			Accept H ₀₅ (z-cal. > z-crit.)
Total	390			390			

Table 4.5 revealed that teachers have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.66 and 0.80 while students have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.63 and 0.75 respectively. With a level of flexibility of 388 at an alpha noteworthy level of 0.05; the figured z-estimation of 0.38 is lesser than the z-critical of 1.96. Along these lines, the null hypothesis is accepted. By implication, there is no significant difference in the mean scores of teachers and students on the Challenges of School-Based Management Committee members in quality administration in public secondary schools in Imo State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Functions of School-Based Management Committees for Quality Administration

The first finding of this study revealed the functions of the school-based management committee for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo state. These include: participating in planning and decision-making processes in the school, Ensuring information on educational issues is adequately transmitted to the school, support to provide funds through payment of fees, Set up mercenaries to check the enrolment of students. Adequate educational facilities are used in school. Also, the finding showed that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female respondents on the level of training on institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in Catholic Secondary schools in Rivers State.

This finding agrees with Kenton, (2019) who asserts that SBMC is seen as a group of people whose responsibility is to train people for jobs, recruit, select, and allocate beneficial programs to employees. School-based management in terms of human resources management aids managers in planning, directing, and organizing the functions of the school administratively. Also in line with the result are Kiragu, King' Oina and Migosi (2013) who stated that school-based management techniques ensure that decision-making authority in the school system is delegated to students, teachers, principals, parents, and community members who act under central government policies for quality administration in public secondary schools to be adequate and effective. The decision made encompasses such areas as funding, facilities, curriculum, budget, and instruction to mention but a few, which are carried out amicably to ensure that quality education is achieved through quality outputs from the school.

Challenges of school-based management committee members for quality administration

The fifth finding of this study revealed that there are challenges of school-based management committee members for quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State These include that: Teachers

notice indiscipline among students, Interference from the students' parents, Lack of qualified and skilled teachers, Unavailability of Teaching aids and materials and technology change. The finding in addition showed that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of teachers and students on the Challenges of School Based Management Committee members in quality administration in public secondary schools in Imo State.

The finding is in agreement with Adeyemo in Asikha (2010) states that unskilled and unmotivated teachers' services can affect the performance of students. In line with the view Oswald in Ige (2020) states that if the stakeholders appointed in schools are qualified and skilled, quality administration geared towards, education goal attainment can be achieved. Subjects are given to those who are not qualified to teach those subjects thereby making the teachers in question impact the learners on what they do not have.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, and the discussions on them, it is concluded that appropriate performance of school-based management committees will improve and guarantee quality administration of public secondary schools in Imo State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the conclusion of the study, it is recommended as follows:

1. The Government at both the Federal and State levels should formulate operational policy guidelines and enact appropriate laws to give legal backing and create an enabling environment for the effective operation of the SBMCs. This will no doubt ensure sustainable improvement in the quality of management and outputs of the Nigerian secondary education system
2. The government, school administrators, and other school members should ensure that those being put in place for planning education programs in our society are experts in education planning.

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